

Active Research: Document

Collect & Create

List Data Types, Formats, and Size

Understand the data you are working with and the implications for data security, data storage, and data sharing. This information should be captured in your project README File, lab notebook, and/or DMS Plan.

- **Types:** List the data you will collect or create, e.g., tabular data, survey data, experimental measurements, models, software, audiovisual data, physical samples, etc.
- **Formats:** Note what format(s) your data will be in, e.g., plain text (.txt), comma-separated values (.csv), geo-referenced TIFF (.tif, .tiff). Using open formats ensures the long-term usability of data and are recommended for sharing and archiving. If you need to convert or migrate your data files, be aware of potential data loss or corruption and take appropriate steps to avoid or minimize it.
- **Amount/Size:** Estimate how much data will be produced throughout the project and if the production rate will change. This helps determine data storage requirements both during and after the project.

Outline Data Collection Methods

Explain how data will be collected and/or describe any existing data being used (including outlining any Data Use Agreement terms). Determine how you will document data collection methods. This information should be captured in your project README File, with links to the appropriate locations.

- **Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN):** Allow users to enter protocols, observations, notes, and other data using a computer or mobile device. Find [ELN guidance across the Longwood Medical Area](#).
- **Lab Protocols:** Describe reusable methodologies in all fields of study. Consider using a publishing platform to collaboratively write and publish interactive and dynamic protocols.
- **Inventory:** Track data files, physical samples, and/or materials using a simple spreadsheet, database, or collaborative tool. Some ELNs have a built-in inventory tracking system.
- **Data Management Tools:** There are many other places to capture information for specific aspects of project management (e.g., OSF, GitHub), or specific data workflows (e.g., DataJoint, OMERO, REDCap).

★ [protocols.io](#) is a collaborative platform for publishing step-by-step methodologies

The Countway Library offers protocols.io Premium for the HMS/HSDM/HSPH research community. Premium accounts expand access to private and secure workspaces, increased storage capacity, and dedicated support.

Utilize Metadata Standards

Metadata is structured information that describes, explains, locates, or otherwise makes it easier to retrieve, use, or manage research data. Whenever possible, it is best to consult community standards. Metadata can be tracked in lab notebooks, lab databases, and/or data repositories.

- **[Metadata Schemas](#)**: Labeling, tagging, or coding system used for recording cataloging information or structuring descriptive records (e.g., MIBBI, ISA-Tab, Darwin Core).
- **[Controlled Vocabularies](#)**: Predefined terms by a community or research group (e.g., CMS coding).
- **[Ontologies](#)**: Variety of controlled vocabulary that defines components and describes relationships among components (e.g., MeSH, MGED, Gene Ontology).
- **[Technical Standards](#)**: Established norm or requirement for a repeatable technical task establishing uniform criteria, methods, processes, and practices (e.g. ISO-8601 date and time format YYYYMMDD)

Create Data Documentation

Good documentation allows you to understand, use, and share your data and helps other researchers discover, access, use, repurpose, and cite your data. In addition to lab notebooks, documentation can be maintained in a variety of forms and will be utilized when depositing data in a repository:

- **[README](#)**: Text file located in a project-related folder that describes the contents and structure of the folder and/or a dataset so that a researcher can locate the information they need.
- **[Data Dictionary](#)**: Defines and describes the elements of a dataset so that it can be understood and used later (also known as a codebook).